

OVERALL DIGITAL SERVICES CATALOGUE

M24 RELEASE – 2024-12-31

Project co- funded by the European Commission within the Digital Europe Programme

Dissemination Level

PU	Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>
CL	Classified, as referred to in Commission decision 2001/844/EC	<input type="checkbox"/>

Deliverable number:	D2.15
Deliverable name:	Overall digital service catalogue [M24 release]
Work package:	WP2
Lead WP:	POLIMI
Lead Task:	POLIMI
Main contributors:	Giulio Fontana [POLIMI], Michał Błaszczak [PSNC], Marcin Płociennik [PSNC], Raffaele Giaffreda [FBK], Davaadorj Battulga [FBK]
Internal reviewers:	Matteo Matteucci [POLIMI], Peter Riegler-Nurscher [JR]
Other contributing partners:	EV ILVO, HISPATEC, IDELE, JR, L-PIT, RGRD, RISE, UCO, UdL, UNINA

Contents

Contents.....	3
1. Executive summary.....	5
2. Recap of M12 release of this Deliverable (D2.14).....	6
3. Evolution of digital services in AgrifoodTEF’s service catalogue.....	6
4. Experience gained delivering digital services to customers.....	10
5. Plans for integration of digital services with AgrifoodTEF’s upcoming digital infrastructure.....	34
6. Plans for integration of digital services with AgrifoodTEF’s upcoming dataspace.....	35
7. Conclusions.....	37

Document Revision History

Date	Issue	Author/Editor/Contributor	Summary of main change
2024-09-30	V01	Giulio Fontana (POLIMI)	First document version
2024-11-26	V02	Giulio Fontana (POLIMI)	Integration of POLIMI contributions
2024-12-04	V02	Giulio Fontana (POLIMI)	Integration of partner contributions
2024-12-10	V03	Giulio Fontana (POLIMI)	Completion of POLIMI contributions, integration of partner contributions to Section 4
2024-12-19	V04	Giulio Fontana (POLIMI)	Response to feedback from internal reviewers; final reading and fine-tuning
2024-12-20	V04.1	Giulio Fontana (POLIMI)	Incorporation of last contributions

1. Executive summary

This document provides a snapshot of the status of AgrifoodTEF’s digital services at the end of the second year of the project. The contents of this Deliverable are focused on the activities performed in 2024 to provide digital services to European companies. They depict a significantly more advanced situation with respect to the previous version of this document, published at the end of 2023 and briefly recalled by Section 2. The advancements of 2024 are highlighted and analysed in Section 3.

The most important advancement experienced during 2024 is that while at the end of 2023 only 3 digital services had been actually provided to AgrifoodTEF customers (all three by Josephinum Research to Blickwinkel Digital Service), at the end of 2024 the number of digital services ongoing or completed is above 20. This is still a low number, but it shows how the efforts devoted in Year 1 and Year 2 to design and set up the elements needed to enable and support service provision are starting to produce the expected effects.

Section 4 provides information about the digital services provided by AgrifoodTEF to customers in 2024. The added value provided by this section (when compared with a mere recapitulation of the services) consists of insights and “lessons learned” that we collected from service providers. Their publication as part of this Deliverable is aimed at helping AgrifoodTEF partners streamline their delivery of digital services in the future.

Section 5 and Section 6 are dedicated to the evolution of the technical background underpinning AgrifoodTEF’s digital services. Specifically, Section 5 provides information about the digital infrastructure while Section 6 is focused on the AgrifoodTEF Dataspace. This technical background, still under development, is very important to support service offer, management and execution during the life of AgrifoodTEF, and even more for long-term self-sustainability.

Section 7 concludes the document.

2. Recap of M12 release of this Deliverable (D2.14)

When compared with the M12 release of this Deliverable¹, the M24 version outlines a very different situation. The main evolution is in the number of digital services actually negotiated with customer companies and ongoing or concluded, which greatly increased: from 3 in 2023 to 23 in 2024 (the latter figure having been evaluated at the end of November). Notwithstanding this development, 2024 is still a transition year for AgrifoodTEF, for reasons that Section 3 will explain in detail. Therefore we expect the throughput of services to customers to increase yet again, and significantly, in 2025.

D2.14, considering that the number of services delivered was very low due to the project having just started its activities, focused instead on providing an overview of the services listed in AgrifoodTEF’s catalogue at the end of 2023. Those numbers were:

- 88 physical services*
- 79 digital services*
- 17 conformity services*
- 26 other services*

These numbers highlighted how, thanks to the extensive prior experience of the Consortium, AgrifoodTEF was capable of presenting to European industry a credible and complete portfolio of services already at the end of 2023.

Thanks to the better state of development of AgrifoodTEF’s activities, D2.15 can now expand its analysis from services listed in the catalogue to services actually being provided to customers. An analysis of the outcomes of these action is provided by Section 4; before that, Section 3 provides a general overview of the progress occurred during 2024 in AgrifoodTEF’s offer of digital services.

3. Evolution of digital services in AgrifoodTEF’s service catalogue

As a preliminary step before a more wide-ranging progress discussion, we report here the results of a new analysis of AgrifoodTEF’s catalogue, similar to the one performed for D2.14 but performed at the end of 2024. The version of the catalogue considered for the analysis was Version 1_10 of mid-October 2024, shortly before the focus of activity moved from the catalogue (which was essentially a list of services) to the much more flexible Online Catalogue integrated in AgrifoodTEF’s Web Portal. More will be said below about this important passage.

The results of the analysis performed on Version 1_10 of the catalogue provided showed that at the end of 2024 the composition of the catalogue was as follows:

- 120 physical services* [+32]
- 118 digital services* [+39]
- 24 conformity services* [+7]
- 51 other services* [+25]

The numbers between brackets show the increase in the number of services with respect to D2.14.

The total number of available services in Version 1_10 of the catalogue is 313, which correspond to 275 distinct services. 38 services, in fact, are “composite” services which belong to more than one service category: for instance, a service may be composed of two well-defined sub-services, one physical and one digital. It’s worth mentioning that wherever this is feasible AgrifoodTEF promotes modularisation of services, i.e. definition of independent sub-services as separate entities that can be combined but can also be exploited independently, so over time we expect the occurrence of “composite” to become rarer.

It is also important to point out that the separation of services into “digital”, “physical” and “conformity-related”, though convenient for analysis and for the association of services to Work Packages, is not an element used by AgrifoodTEF for service classification or selection by their users via the Online Catalogue. Such separation of services –useful in the context of this Deliverable– is also subject to a degree of arbitrariness, so its ultimate usefulness is more qualitative than quantitative.

Figure 1 (below) provides a comparison between the service offer of AgrifoodTEF at the end of 2023 (catalogue Version 1_1) and at the end of 2024 (catalogue Version 1_10).

AgrifoodTEF services

increase in service offering 2024 vs 2023

Figure 1: Comparison between services in the AgrifoodTEF catalogue at the end of 2024 vs the end of 2023.

Overall, the numbers for 2024 show a notable increase (+49%) in the total number of services available in the catalogue. The main points of evolution concern digital services and particularly “other services”, i.e. those that do not fit easily in the other categories.

A possible interpretation of the large increase in “other” services is that as partners become more confident in the machinery of service offer and provision in the context of AgrifoodTEF, they also feel more secure in expanding the scope and range of their services, bringing more of their internal competencies to AgrifoodTEF.

For what concerns the increase in the number of digital services, the evolution can be linked to an expansion from simpler services such as dataset provision to more complex ones such as training of machine learning algorithms, or even more specialised ones. This expansion is partly due to requests from companies, which pushed project partners to define new services that later become part of the general catalogue. Here, too, we notice an effort by partners to offer customers, in the form of AgrifoodTEF services, wider access to their technical capabilities with respect to 2023. This is a positive development since it both expands the catalogue of services and -over time- it promotes convergence and synergy. In fact, as multiple partners end up providing similar services, it opportunities emerge to compare their implementations and to align them, also opening up the possibility to identify and define “best practices” in the process.

It is worth noting that the kind of “customer push” described above with respect to digital services is a major force towards the expansion and evolution of all of AgrifoodTEF’s catalogue. As companies get in contact with AgrifoodTEF services, partners gain a better understanding of the type of services that they need and look for, and are therefore able to fine-tune their offering to better match the necessities of customers. This better matching is expected, in turn, to make AgrifoodTEF’s catalogue more attractive to prospective customers, and ultimately to promote the usage of services by European companies.

In the preceding part of this section we made reference to the shift from the initial list-like form of AgrifoodTEF’s service catalogue to its final form, i.e. an interactive selection tool integrated into the Web Portal. This shift started at the end of 2024 and is currently fully underway. The process of bringing services to the Online Catalogue is very important to improve the visibility and impact of the services towards prospective customers: in particular, the Online Catalogue incorporates the category-based service selection mechanism outlined in Deliverable D2.1 (“Digital infrastructure requirements and initial catalogue of services”), designed to let customers quickly find services of their own interest among the large number of services available, using criteria based on the user’s own needs.

The shift from the list-like original catalogue to the interactive Online Catalogue within the Web Portal requires, however, to rethink and re-describe each one of AgrifoodTEF’s services. Stricter guidelines on service content and description are now in place, and only services that comply with these guidelines get represented on the Web Portal; a revision process involving technical and formal stages ensures the quality of service descriptions in the Online Catalogue.

As a result of the migration to the Web Portal described above, all project partners are currently busy updating the descriptions of their pre-existing services to make them compliant with the new guidelines and thus suitable for publication on the Portal, and significant effort is being devoted to the review of content and form of the updated service descriptions. For many partners, this is also the occasion to fine-tune and expand their service offering. For these reasons, this Deliverable is a snapshot of a transition phase in the life of AgrifoodTEF’s service catalogue. We expect that, at M36, the next yearly revision of this Deliverable will describe a stabilised situation where the only relevant service repository is the Online Catalogue integrated into the Web Portal.

4. Experience gained delivering digital services to customers

This section provides information about the delivery of digital services to AgrifoodTEF customers during 2024. The following considers service instances for which the process of execution has been at least initiated, i.e. for which a Service Request Form has been submitted to the Onboarding Committee of AgrifoodTEF.

Submission of the Service Request Form is usually done by the partner offering the service, on behalf of the company requesting it. The Form contains brief descriptions of the company, of the needs that the AgrifoodTEF service(s) will fulfill, and of the specific services that will be provided to the customer by the service provider. The Onboarding Committee of AgrifoodTEF is in charge of examining and approving (or rejecting) the service request; AgrifoodTEF maintains an archive of all submitted Service Request Forms.

As already explained, the following of this section is composed of tables, each comprising a description of an instance of an AgrifoodTEF digital service. The tables refer to services which have been initiated in 2024. The information in each table has been provided by the partner providing the service.

The execution state differs among the service instances described below. Precisely, the life of a service has been subdivided into three phases:

- “not started yet”, i.e. negotiated but still waiting for activities to start;
- “ongoing”, i.e., while execution is taking place;
- “concluded”, i.e. after execution (analysis of results that can be either ongoing or completed).

The most important information that the service providers were asked to provide via the tables are the *lessons learned while progressing along the life of the service*, up to the phase it reached at the time of writing. This section should therefore be considered as a repository of “shareable insights and experiences” concerning digital services.

For digital services that were part of a “service package” described by a single Service Request Form, the table refers to *all the digital services which belong to the package*, since their delivery is expected to be tightly connected. The table does not consider, instead, any non-digital services possibly included in the package.

In the tables below the symbol “---” characterises phases of a service that did not provide shareable insight (usually because they did not take place yet).

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00179 - Desk assessment activities for digital systems and/or data						
Partner providing the service(s)	POLIMI – Politecnico di Milano						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	Barbieri (Italy) is a company that produces a range of machines for small-scale agriculture and garden use. Their product lineup includes motor hoes, motor mowers, motocultivators, flail mowers, and remote-controlled equipment.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	Selection of the most appropriate sensors and associated hardware for a device under development. The device aims at using advanced sensor perception and data processing to solve agricultural problems.						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	This service represents the first step in a process that involves several other AgrifoodTEF services, as well as activities performed by the customer on their own. Other steps of the process include: setup of device prototype; validation of prototype in real-world conditions; collection of performance data in real-world conditions; evaluation of performance data.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	It is not straightforward to map the needs of the customer onto specific AgrifoodTEF services, as every customer has different needs and –most importantly– a different way to see them. This heavily influences the type of request that they make. Experience gained with this customer and others shows that AgrifoodTEF services almost need to be designed <i>ad hoc</i> for each customer, which conflicts with the necessity to have a stable catalogue of standardised services. A possible approach to tackle this conflict is to design catalogue services to be general and wide-ranging, and to leave specificities to “specialised” services that are customised versions of the general ones, possibly also included in the catalogue alongside the general services.						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00101 – Data analysis					
Partner providing the service(s)	IDELE - Institut de l'Élevage					
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	Adice - Conseil Elevage Ardèche Drôme et Isère (France) is a French association who provide services and advice to goat, sheep, and cattle breeders in the departments of Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region. The company develops and markets advanced digital tools designed to optimize farm management, such as an innovative self-weighing scale specifically designed for monitoring goat kids from birth to 4-5 months. This scale aims to automate the weight tracking of kids, providing a valuable tool for breeders by facilitating decision-making and enhancing performance monitoring.					
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	The service requested as part of the TEF project involves optimising the current self-weighing scale algorithm developed by Adice and Okteo, followed by the validation of the new version. Although a basic algorithm is already in place, it does not allow for precise weight measurement of all kids, regardless of their age. Inaccuracies persist in data processing and weight following, leading to evaluation errors.					
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	The aim of this service is to share Idele's expertise with Adice in the field of artificial intelligence to make the algorithm more robust and efficient, capable of automatically adapting to various farming conditions, while providing breeders with a reliable tool to manage and optimize the growth of their animals. For improving the algorithm, currently based on set rules, Idele proposes the integration of advanced artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques. These new approaches will not only enable automatic data cleaning but also ensure the selection of the most accurate weight and effective following of the kids' growth over time.					
Service execution state	Not started yet	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Ongoing	<input type="checkbox"/>	Completed	<input type="checkbox"/>
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	This service request came from a longer collaboration with the customer. Following a first trial of the prototype during summer 2024, Idele and the customer were willing to go further in the collaboration about this self-weighing scale for kids and searching for ways to fund this work. That's how we decided to fund it through AgrifoodTEF as it checked all the boxes and purposes of the AgrifoodTEF project, and the customer was eligible. After that, it was just a discussion on customisation of a service we were already offering in AgrifoodTEF.					
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---					
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---					

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00201 - Crop classification evaluation						
Partner providing the service(s)	UCO – University of Córdoba						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	Hyperplan (France) is a French software startup that operates internationally across various regions and European countries. The company specializes in developing SaaS solutions tailored for the agricultural sector, designed to enhance decision-making processes for agri-food chain companies. Its platform assists users in anticipating risks related to agronomic uncertainties, such as crop yield, quality, and optimal harvesting periods. A core feature of Hyperplan’s platform is its crop-based land classification functionality, which is now being evaluated for accuracy in Andalusia, southern Spain.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	The customer seeks to test and validate their crop identification functionality at the parcel scale within the Andalusian region. Although the model has been trained and validated with data from other regions, this testing phase in Andalusia is crucial to identify potential adjustments and enhancements specific to local conditions. Insights from this evaluation will allow Hyperplan to focus development efforts on final improvements, optimizing the model's performance for wider application.						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	Evaluation of the functionality of crop classification at parcel scale based on satellite remote images through a platform specialized in agricultural crop management. Quality assessment will be carried out using CAP data from previous agricultural campaigns. The validation will be applied in Andalusia (Spain), taking into consideration agroclimatic conditions and crop phenology in this area.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	The onboarding process with Hyperplan has been seamless, with a clear alignment in project objectives. The main challenge has been prioritizing tasks, as the company is highly invested in both this project and in testing several other solutions currently under development. Defining priorities required careful consideration to ensure that resources were optimally allocated, balancing the immediate need for crop classification validation in Andalusia with Hyperplan’s broader interest in exploring additional functionalities.						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00242 - HPC performance testing						
Partner providing the service(s)	UCO - Universidad de Córdoba						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	Microfy Systems (España) is a company that develops affordable, automated AI-powered digital microscopes for the food industry, with ready-to-use solutions for quality inspection.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	As described by the customer: "Currently, the AI models are cloud-based. Our company has done 2 attempts to migrate the models to the Edge, specifically NVIDIA Jetson Nano, but the GPU provided by these devices are not powerful enough to allow processing of our pipelines. In that sense, our aim is to be able to try if we can migrate the models for specific applications such as spore counting and pollen analysis (within the honey/apiculture industry) to a larger device, such as Jetson Orin Nano."						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	Evaluate the following AI pipelines <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preprocessing steps with traditional computer vision • Postprocessing steps with traditional computer vision • Segmentation models • Detection models • Multiclass Classification models (Transformers) and provide an assessment of the possibility to migrate them to the edge maintaining acceptable inference time.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	After the onboarding, the company decided not to proceed with service execution. However, the company is genuinely very interested in the project, and we are currently providing several services to them, both through the University of Córdoba and other entities associated with the Spanish satellite. The situation arose because the initially agreed services were revisited in more depth, and the company ultimately expressed a preference for the execution of a deeper analysis of the algorithms prior to investigating their possible migration to the edge. Therefore, we connected them with other researchers within our organization specialising in that type of activity: this led to the activation of other services, which we are currently delivering to the company.						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00246 - Test and validate intelligent solutions based on sensors to optimize livestock farming						
Partner providing the service(s)	UdL – Universitat de Lleida						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	MCSystems is a developer of different devices equipped with wireless sensors used to measure the content of silos. A version of the equipment is intended for use in silos filled with feedstuff for livestock production.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	They want to test the error associated with the measurement they perform with possible recommendations for introducing improvements in future.						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	We are collecting and analyzing raw data from sensors and compare with real data using two MCSystems sensor technologies that are involved in their solution: a laser and a radar. Accurate data is provided by weighting the silo's content. Data is produced on a farm collaborating with this service.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	It is likely we must extend the service to more than one silo. Nowadays we are limited to this respect because MCSystem is still refining the operation conditions of the device. The availability of real data is not easy since there is no direct access to data and we rely on the company collaborating in sharing data. However, this way we can better analyse data as soon it is available.						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00123 (AI hardware performance assessment) S00124 (AI algorithms performance assessment)					
Partner providing the service(s)	FBK – Fondazione Bruno Kessler					
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	GeoInference, Italy, Startup providing AI and computer-vision based applications for yield estimation and sizing of crops.					
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	Optimise the AI-based solution to be more efficient in conditions of edge deployments. Minimise memory, computational footprint and timing needed for executing live processing of video streams.					
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	Assess the software and hardware performance of GeoInference’s BioSmart solution, which measures quantity and caliber of apples based on video input.					
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	Onboarding was mainly done through existing contacts.					
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	The service has been delivered over a period of six months. The interactions with the SME have been more intense than planned at the beginning, due to the need to get accustomed with the way their software had been coded.					
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	The interactions with GeoInference enables us to find additional business opportunities from the Italian Node ecosystem supporting the AgrifoodTEF execution. FederUnacoma was involved in the discussion when it came to finding suitable ag-machinery producers willing to test further the solution on their machines. Revo Italia srl was identified and discussions ended up in adoption of the GeoInference solution with a first joint-sale (Rovo+GeoInference) happening in Q2 2024.					

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00125 Data valorization and dataspace integration assessment						
Partner providing the service(s)	FBK – Fondazione Bruno Kessler						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	AISPOT, an Italian startup, has developed a solution to identify, early on, the presence of “alternaria”, a fungus disease that attacks fruit crops.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	The startup has requested a fresh investigation with FBK experts into their solution's accuracy (ability to identify disease in plants).						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	The main goal of the initial service was to analyze the startup available data, to create a high-quality dataset to be used for finding and evaluating more accurate object detection techniques from recent advancements.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	Onboarding was mainly done through existing contacts.						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	After having developed the mechanical solution, the company has made a data collection campaign of around 6.000 images, of which 3523 have been annotated. The resulting dataset has been used to train a Yolo v3 image detection algorithm. FBK has provided additional validation support by testing additional and more recent image detection algorithms.						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00041 - Providing dataset S00040 - Testing of weed detection						
Partner providing the service(s)	JR – Josephinum Research						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	Farm-ING Smart Farm Equipment GmbH, Austria Farm-ING is a start-up company in the smart farming sector. The company develops smart machines for crop care and provides engineering services to OEM.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	Spot spraying implement called SprayING: The sprayer has an integrated AI-based camera system to detect weeds, which controls each nozzle with high frequency of up to 100 times per second. The Spot Sprayer can be used not only for herbicide application, but also for fungicides, insecticides, and fertilizers.						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	Farm-ING wants to improve its models for the spot spraying system. The services help them by proving additional image data and by testing their model performance. The service is customized regarding the specific crops targeted by the system.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	We had already cooperated with Farm-ING in advance. So, the process was very simple and straightforward.						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	Provision of the data set worked without any problems. The algorithm has yet to be tested.						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00172 - Data augmentation						
Partner providing the service(s)	JR – Josephinum Research						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	Neurinos GmbH, Germany is a company working with farmers, research institutions and food manufacturers to develop platform technology, sensor technology and artificial intelligence in the animal production chain. The current focus is on image recognition for behavioural monitoring of livestock in different contexts.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	Neurinos develops advanced image recognition technologies to identify individual cows within a herd and assess and document their welfare in real time using continuous video monitoring. Additionally, a module of the solution is able to monitor sheep, with a particular focus on detecting signs of impending birth, health issues and general behaviour. The system will use comprehensive video datasets of sheep at various stages of labour to train AI models that can predict and monitor birth events and health anomalies.						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	This service is jointly provided with RGRD. RGRD is providing video data from their barns to improve the models from Neurinos. JR provides a service for anonymization of the video data. Specifically, faces of people in the video are being blurred.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	Nothing noteworthy.						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	In particular, there were problems when processing videos from fisheye cameras. It was not possible to achieve the robustness of facial recognition. Therefore, only the data from normal cameras is used. However, these will not be delivered until next year. There will therefore be a delay to this service and a reduced service volume.						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00318 - Real-Time Data Integration for Smart Irrigation Systems S00319 - Data Analysis for Smart Irrigation Systems S00320 - Optimized Irrigation Scheduling for Smart Agriculture						
Partner providing the service(s)	HISPATEC						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	Wiseconn Ibérica, Spain is a company specializing in irrigation valve control systems for micro and pivot irrigation. Their solution is based on a wireless network that allows monitoring of crucial factors in crops, such as climatic conditions and soil moisture levels. This facilitates more efficient irrigation management, optimizing water use and improving agricultural yields.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	These services help agricultural companies test how to improve water efficiency through irrigation data analysis and the provision of actionable insights. These clients will gain a deeper understanding of water usage, soil conditions, and optimal irrigation schedules, leading to reduced water waste, increased crop yield, and cost savings. It also enhances decision-making with real-time data integration.						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	These services allow companies to experiment with real-time data and advanced analytics to improve water management, reduce waste, and enhance crop yield. The service includes comprehensive testing and evaluation to ensure compatibility and performance, ensuring efficient irrigation practices and sustainability through insights into soil moisture, weather conditions, and plant water needs.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	We have not encountered any difficulties during the process. At this stage, we are focused on identifying the most suitable location to conduct the experimentation, ensuring it maximizes visibility and dissemination impact.						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00001 Hyperspectral measurements and analysis						
Partner providing the service(s)	EV ILVO - Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	Perkin Elmer develops solutions for laboratory analysis and measurements for various sectors. In their Agriculture and Food department, the company develops innovative solutions for measuring quality of grain, milk and other raw products. Their in-line, on-line and at-line analysers allow their customers to accurately monitor processes in real time to optimize production yield, reduce waste, and control final product quality and safety.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	The company is developing a hyperspectral measurement device which can be used for routine analysis throughout the winemaking process. The device can be used to analyse both must and wine from vinification to bottling. Through chemometrics, quality parameters such as ethanol, pH, sugars, density, etc. are determined. In this service, the company wants to evaluate the performance of the device and the prediction model for Belgian wines.						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	In this service, samples of Belgian wines are analysed with the device and results are compared with laboratory analysis results. Also, the raw spectra are acquired, pre-processed and specific chemometric statistical and machine learning prediction models are developed for potential further improvements.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	We had already established contacts with the company for other equipment. Therefore, the discussions regarding this application proceeded smoothly and efficiently.						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	The service is currently still ongoing. To obtain a representative dataset that covers the entire parameter space, a large number of samples are required, which are acquired during multiple moments throughout the year. To account for annual variability, the service is conducted over several years.						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00006 Agri dataset Generation					
Partner providing the service(s)	EV ILVO - Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food					
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	SESVanderHave is a competitive, international player in the sugar beet industry. As sugar beet experts, they cover every step of the process, from the breeding of new varieties to the commercialization and distribution of sugar beet seeds.					
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	Use of AI for the detection of Cercospora in sugar beets in high resolution UAV imagery. Applying existing disease detection AI-models (developed for potatoes) in sugar beet. Further optimize AI training and model for detection in sugar beet.					
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	Comparison between existing detection models and newly developed models. Comparison between different sensors.					
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	Onboarding was mainly done through existing contacts.					
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	Customer was delighted with the spatial detail that partner was able to provide. Annotation efficiency was also applauded.					
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	AI models were transferable to other crops but required some optimization to be usable. Knowledge about crop and diseases was necessary to translate and interpret model outputs.					

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00004 - Robotic Software Framework					
Partner providing the service(s)	EV ILVO - Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food					
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	Inagro is a leading agricultural research and advisory organization in Flanders, Belgium. It provides practical, innovative solutions to farmers and horticulturists, helping them optimize production, sustainability, and profitability. Through applied research, Inagro develops and tests new techniques and technologies tailored to regional needs. They also offer training, workshops, and personalized advice to farmers. Inagro acts as a bridge between academic research and the agricultural sector, promoting sustainable and efficient farming practices.					
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	Inagro manages experimental fields where various agricultural experiments are conducted. For their experimental in biologic production where a fixed tramline system (3m) is used, they require an electric implement carrier specifically designed for mechanical weed control. However, there is currently no solution on the market that fully meets their needs. Therefore, a custom development is necessary. For the design, they collaborate with machinery manufacturers, but several design parameters are essential to guide the development process.					
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	In this service, two experiments were conducted to gather data for determining crucial design parameters (motor dimensioning, battery capacity). During these experiments, two existing robot platforms were used. In the first experiment, the efficiency of an electro-hydraulic steering system was evaluated. During the second experiment, data was acquired during hoeing to determine the required power for this operation. Two different velocities and three different configurations were tested.					
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	We already had good contacts with Inagro, including a collaboration in the Interreg CIMAT project where we developed an electrical 4-wheel drive, 4-wheel steering robot for mechanical and thermal weed control. That was the reason they contacted us for this experiment. Therefore, the onboarding process went smoothly.					
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	Initially, tests were planned to be conducted at fields from Inagro, but this proved difficult to arrange due to specific field and weather conditions. Therefore, tests were conducted at EV ILVO fields and were performed very efficiently. Data was logged to a timeseries database, which was coupled to the ILVO ARTOF robot software framework.					
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	Having robots with specific drive systems available has proven very useful for conducting these types of tests, especially because they are equipped with our own developed software framework, ARTOF. This framework allows various machine parameters to be captured and logged with an exact link to their position (RTK-GNSS). This data can be captured under realistic and representative field conditions during actual field operations, making it particularly valuable for designers of agricultural robots or implements. To better interpret the results, also the electro-mechanical efficiency of the drive system was tested on a parking lot. From these tests it became clear that a more standardized and automated way of executing these efficiency tests would be very beneficial.					

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	Design and implementation of certified smart irrigation systems						
Partner providing the service(s)	UNINA - Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	Farzati Spa is an innovative SME registered in the special register of Innovative SMEs at the Chamber of Commerce of Salerno – ITALY. Farzati Spa is committed to improving the quality of life for individuals and the environment through innovative solutions for the traceability and safety of products, processes, and supply chains.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	BluDev® is an advanced technology developed by Farzati S.p.A., aiming to revolutionize the traceability of "Made in Italy" products through the creation of a "Bio Digital Fingerprint" – The company wants to expand/further develop the use of this technology for the certification of smart irrigation systems.						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	This service represents the first attempt to certify applications of smart irrigation systems to a tomato crop and strawberry. This technology utilizes principles of blockchain, sensors integration and artificial intelligence to ensure a sustainable water use in agricultural production.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	We have done a first year testing of the technology in indoor and field cultivation systems. We are collecting data and fine-tuning a few parameters related to optimal water distribution, product yield and quality, and technology of water certification consumption.						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	Aligning different stakeholders to improve and test the technology in a real agricultural context is challenging. We need a second year testing/validation.						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00022 - Virtual training or validation of crop and weed detection						
Partner providing the service(s)	RISE - Research Institutes of Sweden						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	CrossControl AB, Sweden supports customers in making industrial vehicles and machines smarter, safer and more productive. Through operational excellence and engineering expertise, the company is a trusted partner for OEMs and system integrators across the world, providing powerful platforms for machine intelligence, communication and human-machine interaction.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	The customer has developed AI-based image classification models, trained to recognize various weeds and/or crops in field images and would like to assess their generalisation properties and identify avenues for further development.						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	Evaluation of CrossControl's AI-based image classification models for crop and weed detection on RISE open Weeds database. Recommendations of methodology for further improving CrossControl's AI-based image classification and/or object detection systems, including hardware performance review.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	Contract negotiations are ongoing and there are still outstanding differences between RISE and CrossControl that must be addressed. The issues are mostly of a technical and operational nature and both teams expect that they can be bridged. Of particular importance is the fact that CrossControl, as a company focusing on high TRL levels, must feel comfortable with the setup deployed by AgrifoodTEF.						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S000219 Evaluation of applied natural language processing						
Partner providing the service(s)	RISE - Research Institutes of Sweden						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	Green Adviser AB, Sweden combines advanced AI with green industry knowledge to provide personalized insights and science-based answers for solutions for sustainable agriculture.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	Green Adviser would like to receive advice on methodology for improving and systematically evaluating the quality of natural language processing (NLP) applied by the service agda.ai.						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	The service will focus on two aspects. Firstly, on tailoring information extraction by designing and evaluating methodology for improving extraction of data from a knowledge base. Secondly, on quantitative evaluation by designing a pipeline for systematic evaluation of agda.ai using annotated data and user data.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	RISE and Green Adviser have collaborated previously and are well acquainted with each other. Green Adviser AB was aware of procedural requirements for AgrifoodTEF services and both contract negotiations and client onboarding went smoothly.						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	<p>Despite RISE being familiar with the product being tested, the complexity of Green Adviser's solution requires that close contact is maintained to ensure the best possible service is delivered to the client.</p> <p>Feedback from the client has been prompt and constructive.</p> <p>Work is ongoing, with current technical hurdles being addressed and RISE fully expects to complete the service in a timely manner.</p>						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00036 Datasets					
Partner providing the service(s)	RGRD - Raumberg-Gumpenstein Center for Education and Research					
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	Smaxtec Animal Care GmbH (Austria) is an innovative company specializing in advanced biometric monitoring systems for dairy cows, aimed at improving livestock health and productivity through real-time physiological data.					
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	The company needs reference data on the lying and standing time of individual cows to correlate with rumen bolus sensor data for improved herd management.					
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	The service involves providing datasets from sensors developed by Raumberg-Gumpenstein. These sensors, attached to the cow's leg, record lying and standing times. This data will be integrated with Smaxtec's rumen bolus sensor data for enhanced analytics.					
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	Smaxtec is a long-term customer of RGRD, with a collaboration that has been successfully established over more than a decade. It was crucial to thoroughly explain the context and objectives of the TEF framework to enable the service delivery within the project. While their longstanding partnership across various projects has fostered mutual benefits, they were not willing to pay for the service as part of this initiative. Integrating the existing business model with AgrifoodTEF can sometimes be challenging to align with the expectations of all parties involved.					
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	We have extensive experience with the data loggers used, which function flawlessly. Selecting suitable animals was challenging, as they needed to be evenly distributed across lactation stages, and parallel feeding trials could affect results. Fortunately, our institute's large experimental herd allowed us to find enough suitable animals. It is highly recommended to rely on established processes and methods to maintain customer trust. However, an experimental approach is occasionally necessary to ensure ongoing development and innovation in the provision of services.					
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	The customer was able to develop a new functionality based on our data service and plans to have it evaluated with us in the near future. This represents the ideal outcome, and we hope to achieve similar success with other customers as with Smaxtec. However, the implementation depends not only on the quality of the digital service but also heavily on the customer's own efforts and approach.					

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00036 Datasets					
Partner providing the service(s)	RGRD - Raumberg-Gumpenstein Center for Education and Research					
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	Neurinos GmbH, Germany collaborates with farmers, research institutions, and food manufacturers to advance platform and sensor technologies, focusing on livestock behavior monitoring using AI and computer vision.					
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	The company needs a diverse video dataset of sheep during different reproductive stages to train AI models for predicting and monitoring lambing events and health anomalies.					
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	The service involves creating a video dataset using infrared-enabled BOSCH 360° security cameras, capturing sheep behavior during lambing, pregnancy, and post-lambing under various conditions and at different times of the day.					
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	We connected with Neurinos through a Bavarian network specializing in digital agriculture technologies. Networking has proven highly effective for acquiring new customers and could be further extended to international networks for cross-border service delivery.					
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	Initial challenges arose due to the new Bosch surveillance cameras used, which occasionally limited footage to single-camera perspectives instead of dual views as planned. Testing novel or infrequently conducted services beforehand is advisable but may be constrained by limited resources.					
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	The service concluded as planned. Currently, no outcomes from the customer are available as the video data is still being processed.					

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00053 Datasets - Real-World Training						
Partner providing the service(s)	PSNC - Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center, L-PIT - Łukasiewicz Research Network						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	DigiFarm - farm management software provider, offering e-services based on spatial data, working on the European market.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	Verify the outcomes of prepared cloud algorithms on local data to match market-specific expectation.						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	Data acquisition and provision based on predefined parameters from the real world. The research object from which the data was obtained and aggregated was a series of fields at various stages of crop production. This data is available for customer and or to extend acquisition process.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	<p>1) synchronous data collection from multiple domains requires close coordination and planning of each participant (and source) so that the data maintains its quality and value</p> <p>2) valuable data is often available in short time windows, therefore provision requires internal quality check process and forecasting</p> <p>3) the client is not focused on the methods or means of how the data is being transferred but on rather on research potential and quality (consistency with content requirements)</p>						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00051 AI Integration – Computation Power						
Partner providing the service(s)	PSNC - Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	Seth software - Company design, produce and implement software. Having portfolio and experience in user applications and expert systems for Agrifood branch.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	Processing large quantity of data and training algorithms for stated problem. The problem demands high computing power (GPU).						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	Providing HPC infrastructure for AI, simulation and data processing. Ordered GPU hours (X months x Y hours) GPU access (Nvidia H100) is via SLURM queuing system (containers, private or public, can be used).						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Customer expect clear rules and policies of resources usage, understandable manuals, and transparent reporting on current usage of e-infrastructure 2) Customer already experienced in usage this technology, are more likely to use service, therefore demo-environments are highly welcomed 						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) if stated problem after of set of failed tests will need more improvements possible underestimation of usage of resources may appear 2) Importance of opened line of support due unknown level of experience of stuff working in the name of customer 						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00283 Datasets - provision / archiving						
Partner providing the service(s)	PSNC - Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	E-test – provides innovative measurement techniques for environment and soil science sensing products manufacturer						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	Providing support for improving irrigation control process with acquired data, testing the efficiency of the process of storing data.						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	Processing from different sources (internal and external services) large scale data regarding the soil and weather conditions, during the test season. Data processed and archived in cloud databases and provided with standardized APIs.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) required data quality tracking mechanisms 2) required aggregations methods 3) spatial context required with standardized units and coordinate systems 						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00200 AI Integration – Model Improvement / Adaption						
Partner providing the service(s)	L-PIT - Łukasiewicz Research Network						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	QZ-Solutions - technological company employing AI methods for remote soil quality and composition analysis, based on hyperspectral imaging data.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	Improved classification and regression models, generalizing to datasets collected at different geographical locations and in different conditions						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	Training of a range of diverse classification and regression models for different soil elements, including ensemble methods as well as deep learning models, on different splits of the datasets, and systematic assessment of their performance, taking into account and analyzing the impact of different parameter						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) fine cooperation, including agreement for multiple digital as well as physical services for the company. 2) Specific use case, need expertise knowledge 						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	Customer provided samples of their own datasets, both hyperspectral images and ground-truth data, and information about their pipeline of soil assessment based on the hyperspectral imaging, and we've been working closely with the company to validate and improve their approach.						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

Code(s) and name(s) of the digital service(s)	S00054 Datasets – hybrid training						
Partner providing the service(s)	Ł-PIT - Łukasiewicz Research Network						
Name, country and brief profile of the customer [up to 5 lines]	QZ Solutions (Poland), technological company employing AI methods for remote soil quality and composition analysis, based on hyperspectral imaging data.						
Problems that the customer needs to solve [up to 5 lines]	Overcome and compensate for the scarcity of annotated ground-truth data based on samples collected at different geographical regions and in different conditions with corresponding satellite hyperspectral imaging data.						
Brief description of the service(s) (including any customisations) [up to 5 lines]	Application and testing of different data preprocessing and augmentation methods, and assessment of their impact on the performance of the classification and regression models.						
Service execution state	<i>Not started yet</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>Completed</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(please check the appropriate box)
Service onboarding and startup: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	It was a smooth process, including agreement for multiple digital as well as physical services for the company.						
Service execution: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	On the company's request we performed a literature review of the specific state-of-the-art methods for hyperspectral data preprocessing and augmentation and their use for soil content classification, and employed some of them to prepare the data for classification models training, testing the influence of different parameters on the models performance. The work has been done in a close ongoing contact with the company.						
Post-service analysis: shareable insights and experiences (if any) [up to 10 lines]	---						

5. Plans for integration of digital services with AgrifoodTEF's upcoming digital infrastructure

Building a TEF Digital Network

A sequence of planned and executed actions is shaping the building blocks of a sustainable TEF digital network. These actions focus on preparation, validation, publication, and provisioning of digital services. These activities put a spotlight on the needs of AgrifoodTEF's partners in reference to used digital infrastructure and are highlighting their achievements, especially in using resources effectively to reach a level of service provisioning.

The common denominator of the analysed digital services (that are also in publication process and therefore assumed as ready for delivery), is focus on enabling AI-driven innovation applied directly in developed systems. Excluding broader contextual considerations, three key challenges for digital infrastructure emerge from service publications, i.e.:

- 1) Robust data management
- 2) Diverse solutions testing capabilities
- 3) Improving Tools and Frameworks

Service publication confirms that as well are designed to utilize digital technologies and infrastructure to support the evaluation of data-driven applications, AI models, and related systems. Services share several objectives and features that aim to be also a contribution the TEF ecosystem.

Catching the common

Based on the above conclusions, challenges that must be addressed to ensure a cohesive and efficient digital network are linked with specific actions:

- 1) Robust data management

Effective data management requires standardizing data pipelines. This process is being built to support services like "Data and Media Labeling for AI Training" and "Curation and Provision of Annotated Datasets". Another requirement is ensuring data security and sovereignty, that supports and enhance services like "Data Valorization and Dataspace Integration Assessment". The third requirement regarding data management is a quality assessment process that should facilitates services like "Data Validation and Processing Services."

- 2) Diverse solutions testing capabilities

Creating flexible testing environments should be focused on user support and enhancing flexibility of customization; this requirement is being utilized by services like "Experimentation with Synthetic Data Generation and Data Augmentation Techniques" and "Curation and Provision of Annotated Datasets". Direct AI model optimization is addressed in services such as "AI Performance Assessment and Optimization on Edge Devices."

- 3) Improving Tools and Frameworks

Optimizing tools and frameworks involves virtualization services and services where software being tested runs on infrastructure provided by TEF. This requirement is demanded from services like "Testing of Plant Detection Models". On the lower level of infrastructure direct usage are service that required tools and solutions alignment supports services like "Provision of Cloud-Based Data Storage."

Moving forward

To create a strong, sustainable TEF infrastructure network, the actions listed above need to be solved systematically. This process will operate in a loop - the infrastructure should instantly support the provision of the service itself, but with potential for further networking.

The next year of work should focus on catching “low hanging fruits” already enabled by accessible digital services which could be open interfaces and already produced or being producing data products.

In the coming period TEF participants should agree on taking the minimum effort that each digital service in subsequent publication should include at least one cross-linking element. The coordinating team should prepare a recommendation on which of these enablers should be indicated as a top priority and orchestrate their assembly into an ecosystem. Services that already use federating solutions, defined as above, should be promoted on front office and among partners to be seamlessly adopted horizontally by other nodes in the network.

The most promising context in long-term perspective is a common data flows, regulated by data space and adopted standard, however TEF should consider solutions enabling discovery, visibility and remote access.

6. Plans for integration of digital services with AgrifoodTEF’s upcoming dataspace

For the integration of AgrifoodTEF digital services with the Dataspace, there are three main levels to consider:

1. **Data Discovery and Access:** This involves organizing metadata storage, cataloging, and browsing capabilities for the dataspace marketplace. The primary goal here is to provide a clear framework for publishing properly structured data, ensuring it is accessible and well-organized within the marketplace.
2. **Technical Integration through APIs:** Once data is published, users need a consistent way to access it via enabled APIs, which requires standardized data structures and parsing methods. This means each data structure and algorithm structure should be clearly defined so that users can efficiently extract and understand the information they’re accessing.
3. **Monetization and Value Exchange:** This level addresses the business aspects, specifically data monetization. For instance, in the case of Pontus X (one of the dataspace technology frameworks adopted by AgrifoodTEF), built-in tracking and a connected digital wallet allow transactions between data providers and users, streamlining the process of data acquisition and payment.

The following figure recapitulates the three levels described above and their interactions with the TEF.

Figure 2: Dataspace service integration.

AgrifoodTEF is not a legal entity at this moment, so its dataspaces is implemented as a distributed collection of datasets where each partner is individually responsible for data management and compliance. Therefore, each contributor to the dataspaces must have their data, access, and monetization tools also implemented, according to common AgrifoodTEF guidelines. The role of the TEF is therefore to prepare the dataspaces platform and establish guidelines, making it easier for external users to integrate and access the data reliably. In the future, we aim to create a unified structure with standardized data policies, as part of our data exploitation strategy. This will facilitate easier integration and establish a common approach for contributors, making data accessible through a shared set of standards and policies.

Currently, discovery of metadata and catalog (level 1 of Figure 2) is provided by AgrifoodTEF, utilizing the ecosystem of Pontus-X dataspaces platform (level 3). Considering long-term compatibility and scalability of integrating digital services with TEF dataspaces, we need to implement common standards and data structures and common APIs (level 2). This will make users and developers find it simpler to access multiple datasets and algorithms without needing redundant integration efforts. This consistency would make the dataspaces more attractive and usable for a wider audience.

Ultimately, the goal is to reach a point where any data consumer, whether an outside organization or a project partner, can easily understand and use data across platforms through a standardized approach. Guidelines, common data structures, and shared ontologies will be essential for fostering interoperability and maximizing the utility of the dataspaces. Once we achieve this, integration and monetization will be straightforward and beneficial to all stakeholders.

7. Conclusions

This Deliverable outlines a transitional period in the life of AgrifoodTEF, and of its digital services in particular. There are multiple aspects to this transition.

A first aspect of the transition concerns the evolution of AgrifoodTEF's service offering. Section 3 provides an analysis of how AgrifoodTEF's offering evolved during 2024 with respect to the situation at the end of 2023 (the latter recalled by Section 2). Highlights of such analysis concern a clear evolution in the catalogue's contents, particularly for digital services, and the transformation of the catalogue from a mere list to an interactive selection tool integrated with the project's Web Portal, designed to support easy exploration by prospective customers.

Another key aspect of the transition which took place in Year 2 is the shift of the project's activities from an initial phase where problems were examined, approaches were discussed, decisions were taken and –as a consequence– tools and methodologies were designed and set up, to a second phase where the tools and methodologies started to be exploited by project partners to provide services to customers. Executing services and gaining experience in doing so is the most effective way to identify ways to improve the infrastructure and processes of AgrifoodTEF: indeed, the experience gained by service providers in 2024 is already being exploited to this aim. Section 4 documents this, focusing on digital services, through examples of experiences and insights resulting from the digital services activated in 2024.

A final aspect of AgrifoodTEF's transition of Year 2 concerns its digital infrastructure, i.e. the technical backbone enabling the delivery of digital services not only during the five years of the project but also beyond them. Differently from what could be said at the end of 2023, the key elements of such infrastructure have now been outlined quite clearly, and a roadmap is available. The effort is currently being moved towards implementing what has been defined and dealing with the technical issues associated to the real-world implementation of sophisticated digital systems. Sections 5 and 6 provide an outline of these ongoing efforts.

All in all, this Deliverable provides a (digital services-oriented) snapshot of a project that, having decided where it will go and what route to take to arrive there, is now starting to move in the chosen direction(s). We expect the next version of this document (due at the end of 2025) to show AgrifoodTEF moving at a brisker pace and reaching much farther.

WAGENINGEN
UNIVERSITY & RESEARCH

FH WIENER NEUSTADT
FRANCISCO JOSEPHINUM
Agrartechnologie & Digital Farming
Wieselburg

RAUMBERG GUMPENSTEIN
RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT

ARVALIS
Institut du végétal

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI MILANO

Universitat de Lleida

Łukasiewicz
Poznański
Instytut
Technologiczny

